

Recommendations on Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs) Empowering Deprived through Education NEP-2020: Insights and Inputs

Pardeep Singh Dehal

Assistant Professor

Deptt. of Education, ICDEOL, HPU, Shimla, India

Received : 02/05/2022

1st BPR : 13/05/2022

2nd BPR : 01/06/2022

Accepted : 14/06/2022

Abstract

It is very important for the educationists to play a crucial and participatory role in contributing ideas and shouldering into building a foundation of remarkable education. The NEP- 2020 while offering an exclusive section on Equitable and Inclusive education (EIE) seeks to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long opportunities for all sections of society by 2030. In the higher education where in the students belonging to disadvantaged social groups usually face exclusionary treatment discrimination by some teachers and peers during their studies. As a consequence, it makes it difficult to survive in an institution where the lower caste students do not find adequate institutional support and social space and they are forced in dropping out of their studies. Here, also sometimes systematically filtered out with the arguments of merit criteria and quota policy. Its commitment to EIE is rooted in the global education development agenda of Gol- 4 of sustainable development goals (SDGs) which was adopted by India in 2015. The policy targets to provide quality education to students of all sections and particularly to those who have been historically marginalized and disadvantaged. Fortunately, it aims at achieving the target of gross enrolment ratio (GER) in the case of SCs and STs in NEP-2020 from 23% and 17.2% respectively to 50% by 2035. This target may be achieved by adopting the measures and strategic initiatives suggested in the present report.

Keywords: Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs), Empowering, Education, NEP-2020.

Preface

Empowerment of the Socially Disadvantaged Groups viz., the Scheduled Castes (SCs), the Other Backward Classes (OBCs) and the Minorities continues to be on the priority list of country's developmental Agenda, as they still lag behind the rest of the society due to their social and economic backwardness. Their share in the country's total population is quite substantial, as SCs account for 179.7 million, representing 17.5 per cent and Minorities being 188.9 million, representing 18.4 per cent in 2001 (projected on the basis of the trend of their decadal growth rates, in the absence of the data of 2001 Census). The population of OBCs, as estimated by the Mandal Commission, constitutes 52 per cent of countries total population (appears to be on a high side because of the possibility of certain communities of SCs and Minorities featuring in the list of OBCs). Although many young people are less aware of a class structure operating within the UK today, the legacy of the traditional British class system (Upper, Middle and Working class) remains a feature of our society. Socio-economic groups today are more complex, relating to a mixture of wealth (earned or inherited), earning power, type of work, as well as education.

Income inequality in the UK has increased enormously over the past 50 years, which means that people in the highest income groups have very different lives and life opportunities to those in the lowest. In the past, social class largely determined the type of work you went into, partly because the types of work were representative of a different kind of economy, based on manufacturing and

associated industries, such as mining. There was little movement between classes. Developments in the late twentieth and twenty-first centuries have created massive change in the economy and workplace. Changes in education gave young people the opportunity to choose a career, rather than slot into class expectations.

Rationalisation about Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs) :

These days it is very important for the educationists to play a crucial and participatory role in contributing ideas and shouldering into building a foundation in establishing some of the administrative bodies that are advocated under NEP 2020. It's a great need to form a working group that will conduct wide consultation and discussion on the structural reforms on the proposed institutions under NEP 2020. The main focus should be to organize discussion/ consultation on the important areas as mentioned below:

- Higher Education Commission of India (HECI)
- National Educational Technology Forum (NETF)
- National Research Foundation (NRF)
- Socio Economic Disadvantage Group (SEDG)
- National Higher Education Regulatory Council
- National Accreditation Council
- Higher Education Grants Council
- General Education Council
- Academic Bank Credit
- Promotion of Indian Knowledge System
- Education in Mother Tongue

Dr. Rupal Chowdhari, Associate Professor in Economics, Prestige Institute of Management and Research, Indore. M.P. praised the effort and contribution of private institutions and Universities in upholding the spirit of SEDG. To bring SEDG into the mainstream for equitable and inclusive education, private universities are one of the best catalysts for SEDG. She recommended that career guidance and counselling cell need to be formed in the universities. Counselling of students, seminars; workshops should be arranged for skill- based career options. Counselling parents should be done to make them aware of the courses available for their wards. She also suggested that financial help from voluntary organisations should be provided to the SEDG students.

Professor Badri Narayan, Director, G.B. Pant Social Science Institute, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh appreciated the Special Education Zone concept mentioned in the NEP, which he said is a very creative concept in terms of educational development of the SEDG. This will map the region dominated by marginal communities in population and help in chalking out plans for the dissemination of educational opportunities to the grassroots level.

Professor Prakash Mani Tripathi, Vice Chancellor, Indira Gandhi National tribal University (IGNTU), Amarkantak emphasised that the 2020 talks about high- quality education as a right that must be granted to every individual, emphasising for increased accessibility of socially and economically disadvantaged groups (SEDGs) . A national scholarship portal will be set up and expanded to support, promote, and tract of students receiving scholarship. Private institutions will also be encouraged to offer economic concessions to their students.

Shri Girish Prabune, Social Activist and Educationist said that as enunciated in the Preamble to the constitution of India the Indian, the Indian state strives for social, economic and political justice. With an object to create social equity and perception of justice, the state is dragooned to form policies that discriminate positively in India, the 'unequal' class is an outcome of century-old structural oppression. Thus, to uplift the marginalised and to bring them into the mainstream, the concept of reservation came into existence. The rationale behind the reservation is to provide these people with

an opportunity to thrive and contribute to the nation . The reservation is equally made applicable in public educational institutions.

Lakshmi Narayan Tripathi, Transgender/Hijra rights activist, stressed the the creation of an awareness of inherent equality and removal of prejudices and complexes transmitted through the social environment, especially when it comes to school students who do not conform to the expectations from their sex. There is no reference to include students of diverse sexualities, transgender and gender- nonconforming students, despite a wealth of literature and published first-person accounts indicating that LGBT and gender -nonconforming students face bullying, harassment , physical and sexual violence in the education systems, and dropout at higher rates than other students.

Professor T.V. kattimani, Vice- Chancellor, Central Tribal University, Andhra Pradesh described that NEP 2020 has to trawl and analyse in-depth concerning the issues that our country is facing at the grassroots level the paucity of training personnel and the lack of technological infrastructure in the rural areas. Also, the ECCE Programme focuses to attain learning in terms of cognitive development, socio economic development, physical development, and development in the form of communication, literacy, and numeracy. NEP 2020 has seemingly failed to ponder on the needs of our country, where there is a massive divide in the name of the language, caste, resources, which in turn put up the immense difficulties to climb up the ladder of social and economic inequality. The government should try to eliminate the gap left in the NEP 2020 in terms of language problems, technological impediments and should aim at fostering the growth of every brain by giving access to all resources.

Strategic Initiatives, Insights and Suggestions-

Some very valuable strategic suggestions and insights for implementations for SEDG empowerment through NEP-2020 are :

1. To increase access/ GER and controlling dropout rate

- **Institutional equity:** The colleges and Universities established in the area of the larger population of SCs and STs or those institutions wherein students belonging to these groups are enrolled in the majority should be given preferential treatment in terms of the special financial package, recruitment of teachers belonging to the same caste/ tribe and linguistic groups.
- Reservation policy both for sanctioned seats of students and teaching positions of all private higher education Institution should be implemented in letter and spirit.
- At least two special higher education residential institutions/colleges in tune with Navodaya school system should be established for SCs/ STs stake holders of the concerned districts.
- Flexibility in admission: The students whose final result is awaited or have some health problem may be allowed or promoted in the next academic session.
- The students from educationally backward districts and regions should be given deprivation points in admissions such as five points for male students it and 10 points for female students.
- First generation learners for parents with little schooling or without assured income may be given preference in admission, scholarship and hostel accommodation.
- First generation learners for parents with little schooling or without assured income may be given preference in admission, scholarship and hostel accommodation.
- Every eligible aspiring student belonging to SEDGs who wishes to join a research programme Ph.D. and another research degree should be mandatory provided supervisor by the concerned institution. And, it should be also mandatory for every teacher in university and Research Institute to allot 15% seats in case of SC and 7.5% in ST categories respectively or as per reservation policy of state government out of the seats allotted to him/her.

2) To ensure Timely Financial Help and providing a Safe and Secure environment

- Special financial package and provision for the promotion of education of students belonging to nomadic, Semi-nomadic and de-notified tribes should be provided by union government, state governments and HEIs.
 - The scholarships and incentive schemes should be in agreement with National Dearness Index and be disbursed every month. Besides, College and University authorities are made accountable for timely disbursing the scholarship to students.
 - Means cum Merit Scholarship should be introduced at the PG level on the pattern of JNU, New Delhi. The student with a minimum grade is entitled to get such a scholarship. The scholarship amount may be equivalent to the hostel mess bill.
 - Railway Ticket concession may be given to PG and Research students to visit hometown during winter and summer vacations.
 - A Coordinator should be appointed at both college and university level coordination between funding agencies and HEIs.
 - A female student forum for students belonging to SCs and STs, EWS, should be established at each college and university so that they can get a platform to share their talent and it gives space to create learning and develop their exposure.
 - Every HEI should be provided with effective, efficient and safe infrastructure including multi-cultural classrooms. And vulnerable group- friendly environment in college campuses should be developed so that their proper care may be taken from all aspects.
 - Short Term Research programmes should be introduced for vulnerable groups with credit points aiming to provide them research training before they join Research Degree Programme.
- 3) **To promote communication skills and technology**
- Communication skill centres for SEDGs should be established at both Secondary Education and Higher Education level in each college and university so that their communication skill, knowledge is developed similar to General Category students so that they can complete with students of general and elite class.
 - A well- equipped computer centre along with teachers and staff should be established for students belonging to SEDGs at college and University campuses.
 - Each student belonging to SEDG should be provided a computer for taking down notes.
- 4) **To increase awareness about the creation of an inclusive environment**
- Teachers sensitizing programmes to change the mindset in favour of equal and respectable behaviour towards students of marginalized and underprivileged section in particular and their masses, in general, should be organised by authorities of HEIs.
 - One week compulsory social outreach programme or camp for every student is held in slum area of vulnerable groups and tribal areas in a year as part of Curriculum.
 - The college and university should sign a memorandum of understanding with NGOs and social organisations mutually and work together for eradicating those social customs, traditions and practices that lead to justify and continue caste discrimination and untouchability.
- 5) **Monitoring progress related to GER/Admission of SEDGs in colleges and Universities.**
- Establishment of equity and inclusion centre in every University.
 - A committee comprising officers and outside members belonging to SCs/ STs and EWS categories are attached with this centre.
- 6) **Special cautions and suggestions for scheduled tribe children emerged from IGNTU experiment:**
- Physical access to schooling should be concentrated on.
 - Hostels are critical for children. Seasonal migration is common in several tribal areas. Facilities like seasonal hostels should be provided in all such areas with a high incidence of

migration to help retaining children in the village when parents migrate. In some very remote tribal pockets, for example in north-eastern states, teachers posted to schools are unable to get local accommodation on rent.

- Teacher absenteeism is a major problem in the remote areas.
- Qualified and trained teachers are needed to teach in tribal- dominated Schools.
- Multilingual education programme that start with education in the child's mother tongue and then transit to the regional or state language and English need to be implemented on a larger scale, especially in remote tribal areas.
- Teaching- Learning material needs to incorporate the life situations of children to which they can relate.
- Special training programme for teachers and resource persons to deal with issues of diversity and discrimination within the classroom.
- Allocation of resources preferably for promoting education disadvantaged groups.

Key Recommendations

- 1) Awareness of SEDG should be made to the general public and targeted stakeholders.
- 2) Opening of schools every 2 to 3km is essential.
- 3) Vocational should be given to these groups. Vocational training is made at par with classroom education.
- 4) Sensitizing teaching, non-teaching staff and administration is of utmost importance.
- 5) Career guidance and Counselling Cell for all the SEDGs, mentoring facility.
- 6) Promotion of the local languages, the study material to students may be provided in local Indian languages.
- 7) The NEP 2020 policy should be implemented properly. Implantation of multi-level of entry should be implemented as soon as possible, which will help in reducing the dropouts.

Conclusion

It is significant to note that education which has been one of the leading instruments both in promoting and preventing social mobility the discrimination and exclusion predominantly work as a force. And, It is the higher education where in the students belonging to disadvantaged social groups usually face exclusionary treatment discrimination by some teachers and peers during their studies. As a consequence, it makes it difficult to survive in an institution where the lower caste students do not find adequate Institutional support and social space and they are forced in dropping out of their studies. Further, they are also sometimes systematically filtered out with the arguments of merit criteria and quota policy.

The NEP- 2020 while offering an exclusive section on Equitable and Inclusive education (EIE) seeks to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long opportunities for all sections of society by 2030. Its commitment to EIE Is rooted in the global education development agenda of Gol- 4 of sustainable development goals (SDGs) which was adopted by India in 2015. The policy targets to provide quality education to students of all sections and particularly to those who have been historically marginalized and disadvantaged. Fortunately, it aims at achieving the target of gross enrolment ratio (GER) in the case of SCs and STs in NEP-2020 from 23% and 17.2% respectively to 50% by 2035. This target may be achieved by adopting the measures and strategic initiatives suggested in the present report.

References:

1. DraftNational Education Policy 2019, <https://innovate.mygov.in/wpcontent/uploads/2019/06/mygov15596510111.pdf> [3] Aithal, P. S. & Aithal, Shubhrajyotsna (2019).
2. Analysis of Higher Education in Indian National Education Policy Proposal 2019 and its Implementation Challenges. International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML), 3(2), 1-35. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.3271330>. 17 [4] National Education Policy 2020.

3. https://www.mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/nep/NEP_Final_English.pdf referred on 10/08/2020. [5] Onwuegbuzie, A. J., Dickinson, W. B., Leech, N. L., & Zoran, A. G. (2009).
4. Nandini, ed. (29 July 2020). "New Education Policy 2020 Highlights. School and Higher Education to see major changes". Hindustan Times.
5. Jebaraj, Priscilla (2 August 2020). "The Hindu explains | what has the National Education Policy 2020 proposed?" The Hindu. ISSN 0971-751X
6. Chopra, Rithika (2 August 2020). "Explained: Reading the new National Education Policy 2020". The Indian Express.
7. Shukla, Amandeep (29 July 2020). "New Education Policy 2020: NEP moots professional standards for teachers". Hindustan Times.
8. Dr. D P Sharma on "The Challenges in Indian Education System". Eduvoice | the Voice of Education Industry. 25 May 2020.

